

MODE-II DYNAMIC CRACK INITIATION AND PROPAGATION BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER/EPOXY UNDER ELEVATED MOISTURE CONTENT

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Current Work

Goals

- 1 Determine if water absorption has a significant effect in the dynamic mode II fracture behavior of carbon fiber
- 2 Observe if water absorption has an effect on the crack initiation process
- 3 Find a reliable loading method for mode II dominant fracture
- 4 Have experimental data to corroborate simulations

1

Perform **edge-on impact** experiments to dynamically load pre-notched carbon fiber/epoxy samples

- Preliminary study performed with outsourced samples
- Samples manufactured and characterized in house

2

Compare samples **submerged in water** for prolonged periods of time (>1.6wt% water content) with ideally dry samples

3

Use **ultra high-speed photography** in combination with **digital image correlation** to map the displacement field during the fracture event

4

Obtain the **stress intensity factor** from the displacement fields

- Experimental setup based on study made by Coker and Rosakis.

D. Coker & A. J. Rosakis, "Experimental observations of intersonic crack growth in asymmetrically loaded unidirectional composite plates," *Philosophical Magazine A*, Vol. 81, Issue 3, 2001, pp. 571-595.

Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Specimen

- **Fiber:** T-700, 12K tow
- **Matrix:** SC-780 infusion epoxy
- **Layup:** Manual layup
16 plies (2mm thick), all in 0° direction
- **Notch:** Diamond blade saw for pre-notch
Razor blade for crack

Specimen Conditioning

- Samples were submerged in distilled water for 38 days
- Water temperature of 65°C was kept
- Water Content: $C = \frac{W_f - W_i}{W_i} \times 100$
- Where W_f is the weight at a given time instant and W_i is the weight of the sample before conditioning

- Previous research shows a decrease in strength of matrix dominated properties due to moisture absorption

R. Selzer, K. Friedrich, "Mechanical properties and failure behaviour of carbon fibre-reinforced polymer composites under the influence of moisture," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 28, Issue 6, 1997, pp. 595-604.

Browning, C. E., Husman, G. E., and Whitney, J. M., "Moisture Effects in Epoxy Matrix Composites," *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Fourth Conference)*, ASTM STP 617. American Society for Testing and Materials, 1977, pp. 481-496.

Material Characterization

- This fiber/matrix combination was characterized according to ASTM standards:
 - ASTM D3039/D3039M-17 for longitudinal and transverse Young's Modulus and Poisson Ratio
 - ASTM D3518/D3518M-13 for in-plane shear modulus

- Material characterization was performed to account for material properties degradation due to water absorption when calculating the stress intensity factor

Coupon	Fiber Orientation	Thickness, [mm]	Length, [mm]	Width, [mm]	Tab Length, [mm]	Tab Thickness, [mm]
E_1	0° unidirectional	1	250	15	56	1.5
E_2	90° unidirectional	2	175	25	25	1.5
G_{12}	[±45°] ^{4S}	2	229	25	-	-

	Dry	Soaked
E_1	153.5 ± 8 GPa	150.7 ± 7 GPa
E_2	10.2 ± 0.8 GPa	8.6 ± 0.6 GPa
G_{12}	7.6 ± 0.5 GPa	5.8 ± 0.2 GPa
ν_{12}	0.4 ± 0.05	0.35 ± 0.05
ν_{21}	0.022 ± 0.006	0.019 ± 0.003

24% decrease in G_{12}
16% decrease in E_2

Shimadzu Hyper Vision HPV-X2
Max Frame Rate: 10,000,000 fps
Resolution: 100,000 px
128 frames max

Strain Gauges

— Average strain response
- - - Strain margin of error

- Used for triggering the ultra high-speed camera
- Ensures the experiment is repeatable
- Average strain rate of $95 \pm 3/s$

Overview

- Correlated Solutions, VIC-2D Digital Image Correlation software was used
- Correlation algorithm will track displacement of every pixel
- The result is the vertical and horizontal displacement map at every frame

Correlation Details

- Subset window of 19x19 pixels
- Step size of 1 pixel
- Speckle pattern done manually for 50mm lens (shown) and with an airbrush for 200mm lens

Correlation Details

- Subset window of 19x19 pixels
 - ➔ Dependent on speckle pattern size
 - ➔ Subset sizes between 13x13 pixels and 23x23 pixels were analyzed with no effect on fracture toughness results

50mm lens-horizontal displacement

13 pixel subset – 1 pixel step
1,500,000 fps – 200ns exposure – 50mm lens

200mm lens lens-horizontal displacement

- To obtain stress intensity factors from DIC data first a polar **coordinate system** needs to be established **at the crack tip**

- The following model relates displacements (u, v) to stress intensity factors (K_I, K_{II})

$$u = K_I \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} (p_1 \mu_2 z_1 - p_2 \mu_1 z_2) \right] + K_{II} \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} (p_1 z_1 - p_2 z_2) \right]$$
$$v = K_I \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} (q_1 \mu_2 z_1 - q_2 \mu_1 z_2) \right] + K_{II} \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} (q_1 z_1 - q_2 z_2) \right]$$

$$p_j = \mu_j^2 S_{11} + S_{12} - \mu_j S_{16}$$

$$q_j = \mu_j S_{12} + \frac{S_{22}}{\mu_j} - S_{26}$$

$$z_j = \sqrt{\cos \theta + \mu_j \sin \theta}$$

Where: $\mu_j (j = 1, 2)$ are the two roots of :

$$S_{11} \mu^4 - 2S_{16} \mu^3 + (2S_{12} + S_{66}) \mu^2 - 2S_{26} \mu + S_{22} = 0$$

And S_{ij} is the compliance matrix of the material

G.C. Sih, P.C. Paris and G.R. Irwin, "On Cracks in Rectilinearly Anisotropic Bodies," *International Journal of Fracture Mechanics*, Vol. 1, Issue 3, pp. 189-203, 1965.

D. Lee, H. Tippur, M. Kirugulige and P. Bogert, "Experimental Study of Dynamic Crack Growth in Unidirectional Graphite/Epoxy Composites using Digital Image Correlation Method and High-speed Photography," *Journal of COMPOSITE MATERIALS*, Vol. 43, Issue 19, 2009.

- Next we add terms to account for rigid body rotation and translation

$$u = K_I \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} (p_1 \mu_2 z_1 - p_2 \mu_1 z_2) \right] + K_{II} \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} (p_1 z_1 - p_2 z_2) \right] + T_x - Rr \sin \theta$$
$$v = K_I \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} (q_1 \mu_2 z_1 - q_2 \mu_1 z_2) \right] + K_{II} \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} (q_1 z_1 - q_2 z_2) \right] + T_y + Rr \cos \theta$$

Unknowns:

K_I : Mode I stress intensity factor

K_{II} : Mode II stress intensity factor

T_x : Rigid body translation in x-direction

T_y : Rigid body translation in y-direction

R : Rigid body rotation

- System of equations with 5 unknowns and equations for every pixel used
- Overdeterministic system solved using a **least square regression** method

- It has been shown that by transforming the displacements into polar displacements the accuracy of this method is increased

$$\begin{aligned}u &= f(r, \theta)K_I + g(r, \theta)K_{II} + T_x - Rr \sin \theta \\v &= h(r, \theta)K_I + l(r, \theta)K_{II} + T_y + Rr \cos \theta\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u_r \\ u_\theta \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \end{Bmatrix}$$

- Both displacements (u and v) are captured in a single direction (u_r), allowing for the extraction of both mode-I and mode-II SIFs in an accurate way

$$u_r = (f \cos \theta + h \sin \theta)K_I + (g \cos \theta + l \sin \theta)K_{II} + T_x \cos \theta + T_y \sin \theta$$

M Kirugulige and H Tippur, "Measurement of fracture parameters for a mixed-mode crack driven by stress waves using image correlation technique and high-speed digital photography," *Strain*, Vol. 45, Issue 2.

S Yoneyama, Y Morimoto and M Takashi, "Automatic evaluation of mixed-mode stress intensity factors utilizing digital image correlation," *Strain*, Vol. 42, Issue 2.

G.C. Sih, P.C. Paris and G.R. Irwin, "On Cracks in Rectilinearly Anisotropic Bodies," *International Journal of Fracture Mechanics*, Vol. 1, Issue 3, pp. 189-203, 1965.

G.J. Pataky, M.D. Sangid, H. Sehitoglu, R.F. Hamilton, H.J. Maier and P. Sofronis, "Full field measurements of anisotropic stress intensity factor ranges in fatigue," *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol. 94, 13-28, 2012.

- Least regression algorithm can produce different results depending on what values of θ and r you use

i.e. If r is too big you look past fracture zone
- Find a region in which the stress intensity factor is independent of what θ and r values are chosen and that properly reproduces the inputted displacement field

- The following region was selected to use in the regression:

$$-\frac{3\pi}{4} < \theta < \frac{3\pi}{4}$$
$$0.5t < r < 3.5t$$

- The region was found through different iterations and it agrees with results found in literature

L Shannaham, "A Hybrid Experimental-Computational Approach for the Analysis of Dynamic Fracture," Ph.D. Thesis, Drexel University, May 2017.

Dry Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Results

■ Stress intensity factor evolution until crack initiation starts for dry samples

■ Average critical stress intensity factor of 50 ± 3.3 MPa- \sqrt{m}

■ Experiment 1

▲ Experiment 2

◆ Experiment 3

Soaked Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Results

■ Stress intensity factor evolution until crack initiation starts for dry samples

■ Average critical stress intensity factor of 26 ± 2 MPa- \sqrt{m}

■ Experiment 1

▲ Experiment 2

◆ Experiment 3

● Experiment 4

- 1 Water absorption decreased the mode II fracture toughness of carbon fiber epoxy thin plates
- 2 Degradation in material properties was also observed
- 3 Successfully established an experiment for predominant mode II loading

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